

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP8 – Scientific coordination, project management & sustainability

D8.3 Contact database

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Document History

Version	Date	Description	Non-contributor reviewers (if applicable)
V1.0	31 July 2019	First Version	Not applicable
V1.1	01 August 2019	Final Version	Not applicable

Publishable Summary

To create and maintain an overview of all the consortium members during the project, a contact database was developed. The contact database includes both the members of all beneficiaries as the main contacts of the linked third parties and third parties. The database will be managed and updated by the PMO. In later stages of the project, the contact database will be supplemented with an external stakeholder contact list. This will be done in close collaboration with WP6 (cross-stakeholder engagement, endorsement and adoption).

Internal contact list

The first version of the internal contact list, consisting of the contact details of consortium members, was based on the contacts from the proposal writing phase and all individual partners were requested to check and supplement this list with new members or change details where necessary. In addition to the usual contact details (name, partner, email address), the contact list also contains information on work package members and (co-)leads, management team, managing board and scientific/technical contacts per partner. The first contact list was distributed to the consortium on 4 April 2019 (figure 1). The internal contact list will be updated by the PMO regularly and the most recent version of the internal contact list will be available on the member area, a password secured collaborative website (see D8.2). In addition to the contact list, the PMO created a short manual on how to create an email list from the contact database (figure 2).

External stakeholder contact list

In a later stage of the project, the contact database will be supplemented with an external stakeholder contact list. This will be done in close collaboration with WP6 who is responsible for cross-stakeholder engagement, endorsement and adoption within the project. At first, WP6 will develop and circulate a questionnaire to the other WPs. To, among others, make an inventory of the relevant stakeholder groups for the project or specific WPs. A list of the expected stakeholder groups can be found below in Table 1. Later on, the list will gradually be made more specific and supplemented with specific organisations and contact details. In the end, the stakeholder list will contain the following information: stakeholder group, organisation, personal contact details, relevance for the project and linked WPs.

Discussion

No deviations from the description of work for this deliverable.

Annex

Figure 1: Print screen from the internal contact list (for privacy reasons, the names and email dresses are redirected)

Partner No	Organisation	Short name	First name	Surname	Email	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	Lead	Management Board	Management Team	Scientific/technical contact
1	UMC Utrecht	UMCU				x	x					x	x		WP7	x	x
2	University of Ulster	ULST										x			WP1	x	x
3	Uppsala Universitet	UPPS						x				x			WP4	x	x
4	Biobanking and BioMolecular BMMRI-ERIC											x					x
5	Alma Mater Studiorum - Univ UNIBO							x									x
6	The European Institute for Inr i-HD									x	x	x	x		WP6	x	x
7	KU Leuven	KUL						x			x				WP3 CO WP6	x	x
8	Medicines and Healthcare prc MHRA																x
9	Stichting LAREB	LAREB							x				x		WP5	x	x
10	Agencia Regionale di Sanita T ARS											x			CO WP7		x
11	Karolinska Institutet	KI					x					x					x
12	The Newcastle Hospitals NHS NUTH							x									x
13	University of KwaZulu-Natal UKZN														WP2	x	x
14	University of Oslo Faculty of UOOL						x	x	x	x	x	x					x
15	St. George's, University of Lor SGUL						x					x					x
16	European Institute for Wome EIWH															x	x
17	European Medical Center Grc UMGCG										x	x	x			x	x
18	Orcion	ORC								x							x
19	Institut National de la Santé e INSERM																x
20	BioNotus	BioNotus											x				x
21	Centre Hospitalier Universita CHUT																x
22	Universita degli Studi di Ferrara FERR						x										x
23	Swansea University	USWAN					x						x				x
24	University of Geneva	UNIGE															x
25	European Forum for Good Cli EFGCPC										x	x					x
26	The Synergist and its Mother Synergist									x	x		x				x
27	European Network Teratolog ENTIS											x					x
28	The University of Manchester UMAN						x	x									x
29	Region Stockholm, Health an SCC									x							x
30	Elevate Health	Elevate							x			x					x
31	National Institute for Health e NIHW																x
32	Consiglio Nazionale delle riche CNR-IFC													x			x
33	Fundación para el Fomento de-FISABIO													x			x
34	ttopstart	TTOP													x		x
35	Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezoe RIVM													x			x

Figure 2: Print screen from the email list manual

ConcePTION – Contact list manual

To keep track of all consortium members within ConcePTION the project management office put together a contact list. The list can be found on the member area: Consortium Information (folder) > Contact list (sub-folder) > 20XX-XX-XX ConcePTION contact list (Excel file). The file can be organized by organization, work package, etc. In this way, we can maintain one contact list which can be used for multiple purposes. We kindly ask you **not** to create your own email lists from this main file. Due to the size of the consortium, changes to the contact list happen very frequently and we want to prevent the usages of outdated lists. Below you can find a stepwise explanation on how to extract an emails list, which you can copy-paste in to your email, from the excel file.

PLEASE DO NOT CHANGE AND RE-UPLOAD THE CONTACT LIST YOURSELF, BUT ALWAYS INFORM FLORIAN VAN DER NOLLE (f.vandernolle-raven@umuctrecht.nl) IF ADJUSTMENTS ARE NEEDED.

1. Download the most recent version of the contact list from the member area

2. Organize the table by the preferred group (e.g. WP8), now all the members included in this WP will be at the top of the list

3. Select all the email addresses needed
4. Copy
5. Paste in a document, text only

6. Replace *p by ; (see picture below)

7. Hit replace all, the email addresses are now organized in one sentence with ';' in-between each address.
8. Copy
9. Paste in the 'To' box of your email

Table 1: possible stakeholder groups

Stakeholder group
Mothers, women of childbearing age and wider society
Patient organisations and women's group
Health professionals
Professional societies
Healthcare payers
Regulators
HTA
Public Health institutions including WHO Europe
Pharma industry, EFPIA
Clinical research institutions
Data access providers
ELSI experts
Other: <i>(please specify)</i>